

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

GENRE SPECIFICITY OF AGATHA CHRISTIE'S WORKS

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Abstract

The detective genre is one of the most popular and readable in the modern world. The main elements of the detective story are intricate plots, investigations and intrigues, which attracts readers of different ages. Relevance of the study: the detective as a genre has not been sufficiently explored in contemporary society and is in its formative stages. The purpose of the study is to analyse the popular works of the detective genre by Agatha Christie, to identify the main types of characters in her novels, to determine the characteristic features of the author's style in the works, to consider the subgenres of the author's detective works. The study included the method of synthesis, analogy, deduction, comparative, functional, logical and system analysis. The paper describes the main types of the classic detective, identifies the features of the classic detective, names 12 common genres of popular literature among readers, and analyses 145 works by the writer Agatha Christie, characterising the main characters that belong to 8 popular genres of detective stories, such as: detective, the story of confrontation, adventure story, mysterious story, a mystical story, melodrama, thriller, and quest. This study examines action-packed literature, which is part of a common cultural tradition together with works of "high" and "elitist" literature. A distinctive feature of action-packed literature is its conditionality by genre canon and stereotyping. The most controversial issues related to the investigation of this type of literature include the problem of its genre stratification. The practical value of the obtained results is expressed in the creation of a classification of the works of Agatha Christie, which can be used in literary criticism.

Keywords: popular literature; analysis of works; author's style; mysterious story; fictional character.

1. Introduction

Detective as a phenomenon is diverse and multifaceted. It defines a different story, the characters of which reveal the circumstances of a certain incident that happened in the past. Throughout the history of the detective genre, several forms of mysterious stories have been defined. Each of the forms is a set of agreements on the representation of the victim and suspects in the work, who and in what ways conducts their personal investigation, and what they are able to risk [1].

Art and literary critics have been studying the popularity of the detective for more than a century and a half. All studies somehow come to the general conclusion that a detective is a phenomenon where a logical sequence is presented, leading to a correct and unified solution of the riddle. This alone makes the reader feel like a direct participant in the mysterious investigative process. Detective story is a very popular genre in literature. A plot formula that is unlike other literary genres, because it contains not only a mystery and intrigue, but also an element of surprise, because of which readers cannot easily predict the ending [2]. The classic detective genre originated in the middle of the 19th century with the novels of Edgar Poe such as "The Mystery of Marie Rogêt", "The Murders in the Rue

Morgue", "The Purloined Letter", published in the period from 1840 to 1845. The main character of the plots, detective Auguste Dupin, became the prototype of the popular detectives Sherlock Holmes and Miss Marple by writers Agatha Christie and A. Conan Doyle [3].

The relevance of this study is confirmed by the need to investigate the genre differentiation of action-packed stories from the standpoint of the anthropocentric paradigm, which is popular in modern literary studies. Nowadays, there is a growing interest not only of linguists, but also of literary critics who study various aspects of the detective text, such as narratological, pragmatic, discursive, and other parameters. An in-depth analytical study of Agatha Christie's work explains the popularity of her books and the prevailing image of mass (formulaic) literature, and also determines the functions of the impact of detective stories on the readership. C. Clark, a researcher of the biography and work of the writer, proved in her work that Agatha Christie had a unique style of writing of her own. Clark, in her work proved that Agatha Christie had a unique style of writing with its own linguistic and language elements (epithets, metaphors, irony, comparisons, hyperbole) [4]. J.C. Bernthal called Agatha Christie a successful

commercial writer of the 20th century, and her artistic works were excessively in demand by readers [5]. With the creation of everyone's favourite detective detectives – Poirot and Marple – Agatha Christie has become synonymous with the conservative and nostalgic tradition of crime literature.

According to another British writer J. Lanchester, the meaning of the detective is to unravel which of the characters are not who they seem to be, this causes unprecedented interest and special appeal of A. Christie for readers [6]. He divides A. Christie's novels into three categories: masterpieces, quite decent professional works (most of them), and works with political undertones. No wonder that A. Christie is recognised as one of the best detective writers. In 2013, more than 600 thriller writers from the Association of Crime Writers recognised her as the best crime writer of all time. Her stories are still interesting to a wide readership even after her death [7].

From the above it can be seen that very little attention is paid to the study of genre classification of novels by A. Christie, namely, the classification of detective stories by genre and type, which confirmed the originality of this study. The study is devoted to a detailed analysis of Agatha Christie's action-packed novels, their differentiation by genre, and the analysis of the idiosyncrasy of writing, which creates a unique author's style of the writer.

2. Materials and Methods

This study includes an analysis of the stories of the detective genre of action literature by A. Christie, as well as the use of the main methods of functional analysis, which provided the classification of the detective genre in world literature, and the analogy method facilitated an analysis of the basic principles of the classical detective story in world literature, determined the thematic role of A. Christie's stories in it. This method allows examining certain features of the writer's authorial style and analysing the experience of researchers from other countries in the study of genre differentiation of the writer's stories.

The method of logical analysis provided an opportunity to describe the features of the classic detective and to learn the main functions on which it is based. The method of comparative analysis shows the experience of researchers from around the world in the issue of the writer's creativity and gives an assessment of their effectiveness. The method of systematic analysis helped identify and understand the author's style of A. Christie's short stories in the literary genre and characterise the individual characters. Based on this, it was possible to describe the main attributes of the characters in detail. The method of synthesis explores the differentiation of genres of the writer's work. As a result, the methods of analysis and synthesis are used to clearly understand the studied topic and reveal its general characteristics and principles. With their help, it is worth noting the reliability of the conclusions obtained in the study, as well as the validity of the investigated information. The paper uses an analysis of A. Christie's short stories in world literature in comparison with other detective authors. The deduction provided an opportunity to analyse their

individual properties and inherent creative elements based on the general characteristics of novels. This method examines the basic principles of the detective genre by different researchers.

The material basis of the study was 145 short stories by Agatha Christie with a variety of themes. There was no special selection of works for analysis, their proper correspondence to various subspecies of the genre of literature was considered. To clearly determine the genre differentiation of works of action-packed literature, a content analysis was used, with the help of which the stories selected for the study were investigated, such as: "Poirot Investigates", "Poirot's Early Cases", "The Thirteen Problems", "Miss Marple's Final Cases and Two Other Stories", "Partners in Crime", "Double Proof", "The Dressmaker's Doll", "The Case of the Missing Lady", "The Disappearance of Mr. Davenheim", "The Case of the Missing Will", "The Red Signal", "The Case of the City Clerk", "The Augean Stables", "The Adventure of the Sinister Stranger", "The Soul of the Croupier". This method allowed examining in detail the content of each of them, determining to which subspecies of literature they belong, and considering the main plot and features of the main characters. All the analysed works have the main features of the detective genre (a mysterious event and its investigation, a typical set of strictly defined actors), and a special role of the reader who actively participates in the investigation of the crime, and not just reads the story. According to the results of the quantitative analysis, 60.5% of the stories by A. Christie's are detectives, 17.5% are melodramas, 6% are mystical stories, 4% are mysteries, 4% are adventure stories, thrillers make up 3.5%, quests – 2.5%, and 2% are confrontation stories. This allowed the authors to draw further conclusions.

3. Results

Classificatory work in literary studies mainly refers specifically to the theory of genre. Modern research is aimed at understanding the category of genre, its essential criteria, the search for constants, the logic of the foundation and changes in genres. The detective is a kind of mystery that the reader has to solve, while showing the ability of deductive character, logical thinking, and understanding of human psychology. Undoubtedly, the individual difference of a high-quality detective is the moral idea that is embedded in it, and is characteristic of exposing the criminal. The classic content of a detective story is a mystery – investigation – determination of the truth. It is based on the tasks of combating crime, which describes the difficult process of solving crimes and restoring justice. The rating of a detective story depends on the rapidly developing plot and the intricate interesting intrigue, as well as on the personality of the main character, who is represented in the work by a detective. Detectives who conduct investigations and incidents often portray people who are not related to detective work, it can be a journalist or a lawyer, an elderly man or woman, a young man or a girl. An ironic portrayal of a character is sometimes allowed in world literature.

Detective works do not appeal to all readers, although they develop logical thinking and an understanding of human psychology. Some consider detectives to be an easy and simple genre, while others consider it interesting and informative literature. This genre of literature is popular with intellectuals, an intriguing detective story, its mystery, complex and unpredictable solutions – cause them a certain rivalry with the author himself.

Each author has an individual image of the detective hero, who is endowed with certain moral principles and abilities, their own vision of the environment. These are, for example, independent investigators and non-professional detectives such as A. Christie's Miss Marple or F.D. James' Cordelia Gray. In G. Simenon, it is the professionals, for example, the police inspector Mégrét. Most of the heroes of detectives have a real friend – a partner, whose idea or hint always comes out spontaneous and is not relevant to the case. Although sometimes a detective, having unravelled a mysterious event and found a criminal, refuses to hand them over to justice, relying on their life principles. All this makes it clear that there are no specific moral cases, and only a person independently decides the further development of events. Researchers to date have still not decided on many issues of detective literature and put forward the following classification of this genre [8]:

- intelligent;
- historical and retro;
- spy;
- gangster;
- ironic;
- political;
- psychological;
- mystical and fantastic;
- action-packed;
- military.

In action-packed stories, the investigation takes place rapidly, and the investigator is always in danger. Such characteristic elements are inherent in many works, they are the basis of history, combining the content and form of the text into one whole. The basis of the plot of Agatha Christie's works is a certain mystery, where the central events are a murder or several murders. In her novels, the time frame is not set, it can be an event of one day (for example, "The A.B.C. Murders") or stretch out for years ("Five Little Pigs"). The scene of the incident is also diverse, the events are described within one house, on the scale of a large city or village ("Appointment with Death"). In the works of the writer, there are no bland open criminals, they are depicted as smart, arrogant, and vain. The crimes themselves are committed partly for the sake of inheritance or monetary gain, but often just for the sake of interest. Each of the actors is not like the other and is always remembered by the reader.

Action-packed detectives by A. Christie are represented by many individual characters. These are the spouses Tommy and Tuppence Beresford, the Belgian detective Hercule Poirot, Colonel Race, and the esteemed Miss Marple. All of them are periodically present in the works of the writer in different periods of

creativity. Various images of the main characters are shown by intellectuals, professionals, amateurs, or casual witnesses, but they are all drawn into the environment of unknown events. According to the analysis of the works of Agatha Christie, it is clear that in most of the stories, there is an image of Miss Marple and E. Poirot [9].

The study will consider each of the characters specifically. There are 12 known books about Miss Marple. This gregarious countrywoman is endowed with powers of deduction, extraordinary intuition, a keen eye for detail, intelligence and observation, and she is a good judge of the psychology of others. Marple was a curious gossip, but at the same time smart and insightful, polite and well-mannered, moderately ruthless and possessed high moral standards. Her unconventional thinking and rich imagination undoubtedly helped in solving crimes. A. Christie described her as an old and fussy lady who almost always expected the worst from others. All the advantages of Miss Marple include openness and charm, which aroused the trust of people, and even the police. Therefore, she was part of the village gossip world and always used it to her advantage. Some researchers believe that Miss Marple is the prototype of Agatha Christie. Miss Marple lives according to the Victorian "codes" of the British province and presents in detail the features of the English character, as well as A. Christie, remains faithful to the moral norms learned in childhood [10].

As for Hercule Poirot, he is present in 56 short stories, 33 novels and 1 play. Poirot is portrayed by A. Christie as a retired Belgian police detective. He is rational, logical, and methodical in the investigation of crimes. His image is considered meticulous, the hero is overly fastidious, a pedant, always rearranging things in their places. This mediocre property often helped Hercule solve crimes. In the writer's early novels, Poirot consistently solved crimes, relying only on the evidence offered and his own logic. He is an obvious aristocrat, does not like radio and car transport, prefers to wear a pocket watch, and has one suit. The popularity of the Poirot character increased when Agatha Christie stopped writing novels about him. A controversial issue in the study of action-packed literature is the question of its genre classification. The literary genre is modified in one way or another during the writing of a new text, but at the same time it is presented as a kind of example for the construction of other texts, realisations of this genre – with the help of its own normativity.

It is important to note that the problem of classifying action-packed stories is complicated by genre varieties and their diversity, the boundaries of which are not clearly defined. This is explained by the internal structure of such literature: there is a high degree of standardisation, but at the same time there is space for the aesthetic experiment of the author, who is able to "change the plot and the environment of action in a new way, remaining within the formula" and "give new life to stereotypes." Ultimately, action-packed narratives are filled with hybrid forms endowed with the properties of more than one genre. Their genre affiliation is visible by the properties of the dominant

formula, while other signs determine its genre variety (for example, an ironic detective is a detective with some elements of melodrama). Considering the existing classifications, it is possible to identify 12 common genres of popular literature:

- detective;
- mystery;
- mystical story;
- western;
- confrontation (including the spy story);
- thriller (including horror story and gothic story);
- adventure story;
- love story;
- melodrama;

- fantasy;
- quest;
- science fiction.

All these genres differ in a certain theme (investigation of a crime, solving a mystery, treasure hunt, rescue of a victim), which provides for its own dynamics of the plot and the type of denouement, as well as an appropriate set of argument slots. Having analysed 145 of A. Christie's works with different themes, the paper identifies that they belong to eight popular genres, which are detective, mystery story, quest and thriller, adventure and confrontation story, and melodrama. For a clear understanding of the essence of genres, a brief description of each of them is presented below (Table 1).

Table 1

Classification of Agatha Christie's works by genres of popular literature

Genre name	Brief description (examples of works)
Detective	It is based on solving a crime. The main character is an investigator, he is shown in the text as a professional detective or one of the characters who was forced to become one. From Christie's novels it is noticeable that the central character in most of the detectives was Hercule Poirot ("Poirot Investigates" (1924), "Poirot's Early Cases" (1974)) and the elderly Miss Jane Marple ("The Thirteen Problems" (1933), "Miss Marple's Final Cases and Two Other Stories" (1979)). It is not often that two full-fledged detectives lead the investigation in the works, for example, Tuppence and Tommy Beresford are presented in the collection "Partners in Crime" (1929). Almost always, the detective has the finale of establishing and arresting the criminal, but sometimes in the finale, the investigator releases the criminal, for example, in the plot "Double Proof" (1974).
Mystery	The focus is on the strange illogical facts of an event. In the course of the plot, these facts are concretised, but the overall picture becomes clear only in the finale of the story ("The Case of the Missing Lady" (1929), "The Disappearance of Mr. Davenheim" (1924)).
Mystical story	It has similarities with mystery, but is associated with the presence of supernatural forces. A vivid example of "The Dressmaker's Doll" (1979). In the plot, the doll appeared mysteriously in one place every day, as a result, it also mysteriously and strangely disappeared from the lives of the main characters.
Quest story	This is, in fact, a logical chain of unravelling a certain intellectual task, as in the work "The Case of the Missing Will" (1924), where the main characters had to participate in solving logical tasks to find the will left. The quest story is about mental tension and logical thinking, which arouses the reader's interest.
Thriller	The main character in such a work is a victim of a crime. The situations in which the victim find themselves are emotionally stressful and they seek a way out on their own, which makes the reader interested. A striking example is Agatha Christie's "The Red Signal" (1933). Friendship, love, murder – everything is at the heart of the plot. It is important to note that thriller is the genre that is in demand not only in literature, but also in cinema.
Adventure story	This is an exciting adventure of the main character, who is not a victim of circumstances but voluntarily solves difficult tasks on the way. For example, "The Case of the City Clerk" (1934). The ending of such adventure stories is always positive.
Confrontation	An interesting fact is that the confrontation story shows the conflict of the hero and the antihero. Often this conflict is resolved by the hero's victory, and the main character evokes the reader's sympathy. This genre is typical for westerns, action movies, and spy novels. In Agatha Christie's "The Augean Stables" (1947), "The Adventure of the Sinister Stranger" (1929), where the main characters confront someone or something, solving crimes.
Melodrama	It has a dramatic character, in the plot the personal and everyday relationships of the characters. Almost always, worries about the main character's cause tension in the reader. The ending of the story can be different – happy or tragic. An example from Agatha Christie is the novel "The Soul of the Croupier" (1930). A drama with a happy ending, where a narrative tension is created due to a dramatic intrigue with an unknown ending.

As a result, it can be seen that most of the stories of A. Christie is made up, of course, by detectives. A characteristic feature of the works is their mystery and logical actions of all the characters. The classic rule of her detective story is an intellectual dispute between the

reader and the detective in achieving the truth. The genre properties of the detective are attracted by the stability of stereotypes, the repetition of the main structural actions, and the stability of the composition [11]. In the individual genre of writing novels, Agatha

Christie has preserved the common features of the tradition of the British novel: the simplicity of plot creation, the closeness of the process, a limited circle of participants, and the plot is rationally constructed.

4. Discussion

Agatha Christie is not considered the founder of the detective genre, but is associated with it more than other writers. In many ways, her success depends on her individual writing style. After analysing the works of Agatha Christie, it can be argued that in the genre of detective fiction, the writer is ahead of her contemporaries. It is true to the strict principles of the classic detective, but it is also worth noting an innovative approach. The writer skilfully manages the characters of the characters, twists the plot schemes, always leading the reader to unexpected finales. J.K. Bernthal, a researcher of Agatha Christie's work, believes that she is one of the few who so skilfully compares and re-compares the existing elements of writing [12]. But, for example, the modern English writer J. Lanchester notes that fans of Agatha Christie's work do not consider her to be "high literature", allegedly her characters "vary" between stereotypes and caricatures [6]. Comparing A. Christie's work to detective story writers M. Allingham and D. Seiersy, J. Lanchester calls A. Christie not modern. It is worth defining such an opinion as erroneous, because classical literature never goes out of fashion.

Having studied the stories of Agatha Christie, one can notice a special individual style of writing. Reading her books before the finale of the work, it is impossible to calculate the identity of the real criminal and describe their motives for committing a crime. A researcher of Agatha Christie's biography and works, S. Beyer examines the writer's early work in detail, focusing on the application of key motifs and symbolism to the view of relationships through the lens of romance [13]. He suggests that the novels of Agatha Christie serve as an important creative platform for the study of the relationship between genre, subjectivity, and symbolism. The study contains an analysis of works of fiction, their genre and specifics, it will be useful to philologists and literary critics studying the issue of literary genre.

Writers from Croatia V. Domjanović and B. Oklopčić suggest that while working as a nurse during World War I, Agatha Christie became interested in chemistry (poisons), in their opinion, all this soon changed her writing style [14]. It would be advisable to agree with the opinion of researchers, and add that the use of "poison" in novels has become one of the strengths of the writer's works. K. Smirley investigated in detail the novel "Murder on the Orient Express" (1933) translated into Greek [15]. The researcher describes how Greek translators overestimate the image of Poirot. In the Greek translation, the detective is shown to be more elegant and polite, with a minimum of humour and simplicity. It is also worthy of attention. In this case, it is important to note that the practice of translation has a rich resource in the study of the development of similarities in fiction.

The US writer K. Eckert also did a detailed analysis of the detective work "Murder on the Orient

Express" [16]. He suggests that the novel is the most widely read, and the main character, the Belgian Hercule Poirot, is Agatha Christie's most popular detective. K. Eckert tries to revive the discussion about the murder by finding weighty reasons for its shortcomings. Poirot, in his opinion, contrasts positively with the background of the train passengers. It would be correct to agree with the writer's characterisation, but to add that the imaginary shortcomings of the train passengers also cause the reader to have reverence and sympathy for Poirot, contrasting with his noble seriousness so much that the characters tend to resemble him in grace and generosity.

It is also worth noting the work of J. Gulddal, a teacher from the University of Newcastle, on a detailed textual study of the novel "Appointment with Death" (1945) [17]. He describes in detail the problem of textual and subtextual discussion, Poirot's traditional narrative of criminal retribution and a mythical narrative that links suppression to civilizational savagery with the practice of human sacrifice. It is important to say that such a detailed analysis is worthy of attention, revealing the work "Appointment with Death" from the other side of the genre specifics of the detective, which may arouse the professional interest of philologists and literary critics.

The image of Miss Marple was described in detail by another researcher from Australia B. Köseoğlu, studying it from the novel "The Body in the Library" (1984) [18]. Miss Marple is described as an amateur detective who transcends the power of patriarchal society. Her image among male detectives changes the course of the investigation when she manages to get to the truth and solve the mystery of the crime. Gender and detective are inseparably linked here. It shows how, in an environment dominated by men, Miss Marple establishes order and morality in society, proving that women are just as smart and clever as men. B. Köseoğlu noted Christie's contribution to detective literature through her character Miss Marple, emphasised equality between men and women not only in society, but also in criminal investigations, to highlight the conflict between women and men in society and in the field of criminal investigations.

In this study, in the description of the image of Miss Marple, her excessive observation is noted. Describing this image, the Polish researcher J. Węgrodzka highlighted the metaphysical potential of Agatha Christie's stories about Miss Marple for studying and exploring the conventions of crime literature, in particular, for thinking about the creation and interpretation of stories in general [19]. J. Węgrodzka suggests that Miss Marple solves mysterious crimes only with the help of her unsurpassed insight. In classic detective novels, food occupies a special place. It is often presented as a source of stability and order. Agatha Christie also incorporated eating habits and eating rituals into all her detective stories, using them to create a feminine and domestic hearth.

The study by P. Chakravarty analysed how the writer used the image of food as a tool for further

narration, showing it in her novels as a calming ritual and the key to solving the murder [20]. According to the researcher, Christie's food sometimes acquired a more sinister shade. One can agree with such a judgment of the writer, because Agatha Christie turns food into a murder weapon itself, as a bad omen indicating events, thereby mixing reality with the storyline and giving vivacity to her characters and plots.

Researcher J. Gildersleeve investigated the last novels written by Agatha Christie about Hercule Poirot, "Hallowe'en Party" (1969) and "Elephants Can Remember" (1972), which, in her opinion, are already formulaic, have a lot of dialogues, and "leaky" plots [21]. J. Gildersleeve believes that this is why the writer's late work received little attention among literary critics. With this version of the researcher, it is worth partially agreeing and adding that in the latest novels about Poirot, the detective already looks "tired". In this study, in the characterisation of the image of Poirot, it was said about this, as well as about the "fatigue" of the writer herself from this image.

The modern approach to the study of texts that have gone beyond the literary canons has caused a growing interest in the work of Agatha Christie, but she is still insufficiently represented. Researcher C. Ewers conducted an in-depth analysis of the works "Murder on the Orient Express" (1934) and "4:50 from Paddington" (1957) by studying how Agatha Christie uses the description of train travel in her fiction in order to explore the genre conventions of the detective [22]. In his opinion, the descriptions of travel by train from A. Christie's are not very absorbing. She barely describes the plot of "4:50 from Paddington". And in "Murder on the Orient Express", the writer relies on the fact that readers themselves will find out about "perhaps the most famous name of the train in the history of Zimmerman 15". This version of the writer's criticism is acceptable, however, it is important to say that it is through the use of this image of the "train" that Agatha Christie changes the usual paths associated with travelling by rail, which undermines the reader's expectations.

After reviewing the studies by researchers from different countries, it is important to note that they are all aimed at investigating the work of Agatha Christie within the literary detective genre. The considered analysis of the researchers' activities suggests that Agatha Christie created not just detective stories, she came up with images of characters and often tragic stories, which made it possible to attribute her work to the classics of world literature. That is why the study of her personality and creativity continues, attracting the attention of more and more new researchers in the field of literary studies and other related fields of scientific knowledge.

5. Conclusions

The conducted research provided an opportunity to analyse the genre differentiation of Agatha Christie's works. This paper names the main genres of action literature, reviews the works by A. Christie, reveals their belonging to 8 action genres (detective, adventure story, mystery, confrontation story, mystical story,

quest, thriller, and melodrama), which call out the specifics of these stories and have different frequency of implementation. Common and distinctive features in these stories are the narrative tension underlying their normative structure. These features are conditioned by the genre specifics of the text of the works.

The paper examines the features of the main characters, reveals the author's style of writing, and also presents a brief description of genres with examples of the writer's works. It is also shown that stereotyping and conditionality to genre canons are among the main features of action-packed literature, and the most discussed issues related to the study of this type of literature include the issue of its genre differentiation. The analysis shows that among the genres considered, the most representative is the detective genre, to which most of A. Christie's works belong. Based on the analysis of specific works, it can be concluded that Agatha Christie is, without a doubt, a recognised master of the classic detective.

Her works are much more than the sum of plots, no matter how original they may be; they offer a wide range of stories, new modernistic possibilities of playing with text, and genuine social intervention, which arouses the undoubted interest of readers of the world literature and, accordingly, researchers of her work. Interest in the study of her artistic works does not fade despite the fact that she died in 1976. The analysis of Agatha Christie's work continues to cause criticism and controversy among researchers, the ambiguity of assessments, and new interdisciplinary approaches to the study of works confirm the prospects for further research.

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